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The Crowding of Prisons in the Italian Regions

Between 2008 and 2020 it decreased by about 21.8%

Istat-BES calculates the crowding of prisons in the Italian regions. The variable is calculated as the percentage value of inmates present in detention institutions on the total available places defined by the regulatory capacity.

Ranking of the regions by value of the overcrowding of prisons in 2020. Puglia is in first place for the value of the overcrowding of prisons in 2020 with a value of 130.3 units, followed by Molise with a value of 129.5 units and from Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount equal to 128.8 units. In the middle of the table there are Campania with a value of 105.8 units, followed by Emilia Romagna with a value of 104.9 units, and Tuscany with a value of 103.4 units. Sicily closes the ranking with a value of 88.9 units, followed by Trentino-Alto Adige equal to a value of 77.9 units and Sardinia with a value of 77 units.

Ranking of regions by value of the percentage change in the crowding of prisons. Molise ranks first in terms of the percentage change in the overcrowding of prisons between 2014 and 2020 with an amount equal to 16.46% equal to an amount of 18.3 units, followed by Umbria with a value equal to 16.31% equal to an amount of 13.6 units, and from Valle d'Aosta with a value equal to 15.71% equal to an amount of 13.2 units. In the middle of the table there are Tuscany with an amount equal to -16.55% equal to an amount of -20.5 units, followed by Lombardy with a variation of -17.63% equal to an amount of -26.5 units and from Basilicata with an amount of -18.44% equal to an amount of -22.5%. Sicily closes the ranking with a value equal to -37.96% equal to an amount of -54.4 units, followed by Trentino-Alto Adige with an amount equal to -41.16% equal to -54.5 units. tie with Emilia-Romagna with an amount equal to -41.46% equal to a value of -74.3 units. On average between 2014 and 2020 the value of the overcrowding of prisons in the regions analyzed decreased by an amount equal to -15.47%.

Italian macro-regions. Between 2008 and 2020 the value of the overcrowding of prisons decreased in all Italian macro-areas. The South is in first place in terms of the reduction in the crowding of prisons with an amount equal to -25.43% equal to a value of -33.6 units, followed by the North with a value equal to -23.06. % equal to an amount of -34.3 units, and from the Center with a variation equal to an amount of -10.37% equal to a value of 12.3 units. Overall, in Italy the value of the overcrowding of prisons decreased by an amount equal to -21.85% equal to an amount of -29.5 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm. A clustering is analyzed below using the k-Means algorithm. The k-Means algorithm is a supervised algorithm therefore it is necessary to independently identify the number of clusters to be used. However, the Silhouette coefficient can be used to reduce discretion in the choice of clusters. The Silhouette coefficient varies between -1 and +1. The number of clusters that have a higher Silhouette coefficient value is then chosen. In the analysis of the Silhouette coefficient, the three-clusters model appears to have the highest value in terms of the Silhouette coefficient with a value of 0.336 units.

- *Cluster 1:* Tuscany, Piedmont, Umbria, Sicily, Abruzzo, Basilicata, Valle d'Aosta, Marche, Calabria, Lazio, Campania, Molise;
- *Cluster 2:* Lombardy, Puglia, Veneto, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Emilia-Romagna, Liguria;

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- *Cluster 3: Trentino-Alto Adige, Sardinia.*

With reference to the overcrowding of prisons in 2020, it is possible to calculate the median of the clusters to verify the presence of an ordering of clusters. Specifically, it appears that cluster 2 is in first place in terms of the median value of the overcrowding of prisons with an amount equal to 122.25 units, followed by the regions of cluster 1 which have a median value equal to an amount of 100, 1 and from cluster 3 with an amount equal to 77.45 units. It therefore follows that the ordering value of the clusters is indicated below, namely: $C2 > C1 > C3$. It therefore follows that generally the northern regions except for Puglia have a high level of overcrowding in prisons. While the most virtuous regions in terms of crowding of the prisons are Trentino-Alto Adige and Sardinia. It therefore follows that the northern regions, especially Lombardy, Veneto, Emilia-Romagna, Liguria, and Friuli-Venezia Giulia, which total more than 20 million inhabitants, need penitentiary construction and prison recovery policies, and alternative measures to punishment, which can make it possible to reduce the value of the overcrowding of prisons.

Conclusions. In summary, it is necessary to consider that between 2008 and 2020 the crowding of prisons has significantly decreased in all Italian macro-regions. On average, the crowding of prisons decreased by 21.8% between 2008 and 2020 in Italy. There are, however, regions in countertrend where the overcrowding of prisons has grown, such as Molise, Valle d'Aosta, and Umbria. However, clustering shows that the overcrowding of prisons tends to grow in the Northern regions except for Trentino-Alto Adige which instead has low levels of crowding in prisons. In Southern Italy, on the other hand, Puglia is in first place for the value of the crowding of prisons with levels close to the regions of the North. It is necessary to consider that especially in the Northern regions it is necessary to intervene both with the construction of new prisons, and with new penalties that are alternatives to detention as well as with security and education policies that can prevent and prohibit citizens from exercise of criminal activities.

	2020	Regioni	Cluster	Silhouette
1	106.6	Piemonte	C1	0.635861
2	97.2	Valle d'Aosta/V...	C1	0.606125
9	103.4	Toscana	C1	0.640219
10	97.0	Umbria	C1	0.617776
11	100.1	Marche	C1	0.60077
12	111.2	Lazio	C1	0.567238
13	100.1	Abruzzo	C1	0.615093
14	129.5	Molise	C1	0.516884
15	105.8	Campania	C1	0.552704
17	99.5	Basilicata	C1	0.603512
18	90.2	Calabria	C1	0.594114
19	88.9	Sicilia	C1	0.611997
3	120.7	Liguria	C2	0.595344
4	123.8	Lombardia	C2	0.664963
6	119.6	Veneto	C2	0.640966
7	128.8	Friuli-Venezia G...	C2	0.640186
8	104.9	Emilia-Romagna	C2	0.59648
16	130.3	Puglia	C2	0.650418
5	77.9	Trentino-Alto A...	C3	0.544443
20	77.0	Sardegna	C3	0.538574

